

Blending cooperative learning model and TPS (Think, Pair, Share) method in English subject to enhance 4Cs for Senior high school students

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Abstract

English learning in senior high school especially in Indonesia still face several challenges and obstacles where teacher-centered learning approach often dominate the classroom and relying too much on passive learning methods that limit students' interaction and participation in the classroom. These issues are limiting the opportunity for students to learn communication in English naturally, can't support students' reasoning ability and inhibit students' 4Cs development which is essential for 21st century. Responding to these obstacles, this article aims to integrate cooperative learning model and TPS (Think, Pair, Share) method as an effective combination in English learning. Cooperative learning assist students to gain meaningful opportunities by doing discussion, work collaboratively and absorb knowledge naturally. In the other side, TPS offers an effective 3 steps including individual thinking, work in pair and share the final result of the students' work with a wider audience. Those 3 steps will ensure all students without any exception to participate actively and having their own time to articulate their thoughts before expressing it verbally. By combining this learning model and method, students will not only learn English effectively but also able to accomplish essential competencies (4Cs) that is crucial in a real-life communication skill.

Keywords: Cooperative learning, TPS (Think, Pair Share), 4Cs

Introduction

English learning in Indonesia already taught start from elementary school until senior high school. However, students' fluency and ability in English remains low especially in speaking skill. Although English become a crucial subject in a curriculum, a lot of students are still struggle in using the language confidently in their real-life communication and interaction. This are caused by several factors including lack of exposure to authentic English usage, minimal chance for students to practice meaningfully, and passive learning method that possibly can lead to unsatisfactory result where students are not able to reach the essential language competencies specifically communication and critical thinking. (Boy Jon et al., 2021) state that according to the 2013 Curriculum, learning with a scientific approach

is required to be applied. Through this learning process, students are conditioned in an environment that fosters communication, cooperation, creativity, and invention, as well as critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. These four abilities belong to the 21st century.

The dominance of teacher-centered instruction and approach is one of the main reasons of why this obstacle happen in English learning classroom especially in Indonesia. Learning process are mostly conducted using very long explanations of material, focused solely in a grammar, often utilize textbook as the major source of information and knowledge and students are just passively absorbing the information by listening to the teacher's explanation and take notes. As teachers, we can help our students connect learning with real life and provide them with the necessary skills to prepare them for success in life (Erdogan, 2020). In this case, learning approach like this will definitely lead to the limitation of students' interaction, there will be lower opportunities for collaboration among students and hinder chances for students to use English authentically in a real life. Without adopting and implementing interactive environment and learning approach, students will not be able to balance between theoretical and practical content because they may get the content theoretically yet still face difficulty in practicing and applying the content effectively. In speaking class, teachers are required to create communicative and interactive activities by giving students a great deal of opportunities to practice the target language (Mishra, 2017). Moreover, teacher-centered instruction will also lower the level of students engagement in the classroom. (Ghafar, 2023) students are often seen as passive consumers of knowledge, and they are not encouraged to investigate, discover, or develop their own unique understanding of the subject matter. Additionally, there is a lack of active participation on the part of the pupils in the learning process. This may cause the pupils to get disengaged in the learning process and lose their desire as a result. Therefore, it's important to move from a teacher-centered into student-centered learning approach which is supported by (Namaziandost et al., 2019) said that in recent years, the change from a teacher-centered teaching model to a learner-centered model has been one of the biggest modifications in foreign language pedagogy.

Literature Review

One of the most effective pedagogical approach that has been widely recognized is cooperative learning which is focus on student-centered engagement rather than focusing solely on the teacher's instruction and content delivery. Instead of letting students receive the

information passively, it fosters students to work collaboratively in a group with the aim to address problems by exchanging their ideas and opinion. English learning in senior high schools especially in Indonesia, where opportunities to practice the language verbally are often limited and restricted with a vivid grammar, cooperative learning will enable students to become more confident in communicate using English. According to (Maro & Nurbatra, 2013) there are numerous methods in learning that have been designed by experts to meet teacher and learners goal. It means that teachers actually can adopt a method in order to accomplish both the teacher and learner goal.

Conducting and implementing activities that are prioritize student-centered such as group discussion, peer feedback and review and shared task, students will be able to develop and increase the essential components of 4Cs naturally. (Murphy, 2015) beyond that, cooperation enhances learning in several ways. Weak students working individually are likely to give up when they get stuck; working cooperatively, they keep going. Strong students faced with the task of explaining and clarifying material to weaker students often find gaps in their own understanding and fill them in. Students working alone may tend to delay completing assignments or skip them altogether, but when they know that others are counting on them, they are motivated to do the work in a timely manner. According to (Achmad & Yusuf, 2014) in a pair, the atmosphere tends to more protective and private than in a group. Students often feel less inhibited in a pair, and they can talk about more personal feelings or experiences than they would even in a small group.

Nowadays our students learn better by engaging in a variety of different forms of learning. The educational courses today require certain types of strategies which allow students to discuss issues, solve problems, engage in simulations, conduct research, think critically, cooperate and make decisions (Aeni, 2020). The TPS (Think, Pair and Share) method that was developed by Frank Lyman in 1981 offers a complements strategy that will support students for active English learning further. The steps in Think-Pair-Share technique are quite simple. This technique encourages teachers to ask students to think about a topic, pair up with other students and discuss it, then share it with the whole class (Apriyanti & Ayu, 2020). TPS method will provides opportunity for students to process the information deeply by letting them to think independently in the first step which is can foster critical thinking. While think independently about the information can foster critical thinking, working in pair will allow students to practice communication and collaboration by clarifying and testing their different ideas to each other. In the end, students are encouraged to share and present

their ideas, insights or findings in front of their friends which is may promote creativity and boost their confidence by articulating their thoughts verbally.

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Below is the implementation of TPS method in English learning especially for speaking skill:

No.	What	How	Expected result
1.	Topic and information delivery	Teachers give a specific topic and information to the students. Teachers may simply write “Book” in a whiteboard.	All students without any exceptions received and understand about the topic that they are going to focus on.
2.	Think individually	After students received the topic they are required to think independently about everything related to the topic. For example, if the topic is “Book” they may think that book is a something where we can obtain several knowledge and information. It doesn’t matter about what they are thinking about because here students are encouraged to think freely and independently as long	Students are expected to enhance their critical thinking skill by brainstorm and think about the topic given independently.

		as it is still relevant with the topic given.	
3.	Work in pair	After each student think independently they are encouraged to work in pair with the aim to share their ways of thinking, ideas, insights etc.	Every student are expected to improve their collaboration and communication by sharing their ideas with their partner.
4.	Share to the class	After completing the previous activities students are finally encouraged to share their result of work in the class with a wider audience	Students are expected to have willingness in boosting their confidence by practicing their English especially for their speaking ability.

Conclusion

Several challenges and obstacles faced in Indonesian English learning including low fluency, teacher-centered learning approach, relying too much on memorization and passive learning approach—illustrate the importance of adopting and implementing interactive learning method that can foster student-centered approach. By blending cooperative learning and TPS (Think, Pair and Share) method, it will shift classroom dynamics from passive learning into active participation of the students which can lead to a great opportunities to engage and communicate with peers meaningfully and develop 4Cs that traditional methods often fail to accomplish.

Powerful instructional model that fosters four essential competencies of the 21st century (4Cs) can be produced by combining between cooperative learning with TPS. Through various activities such as group work, peer feedback and review, self-reflective thinking and so on will be helpful and effective for students to gain both the confidence and the ability to use English authentically.

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